

MODERN PROBLEMS OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Anxiety is a relatively stable personality trait that characterizes the predisposition to perceive a fairly wide range of situations as threatening and to respond to them, as a rule, by developing a feeling of uneasiness, worry. Most often, the term "anxiety" is used to describe an unpleasant mental state in its coloring, which is characterized by subjective feelings of tension, worry, gloomy forebodings, and from the physiological side is accompanied by the activation of the autonomic nervous system.*

Keywords: *pedagogy, Sigmund Freud, Rollo May, student, person, anxiety, college, conflicts.*

The idea of the need to strive for success, effectiveness, efficiency of pedagogical influence and interaction, based on a certain goal-setting, actually arose together with pedagogy, with ideas about management in general and management of children and schools in particular. One of the ancient logics of the connection between pedagogical goals and results was expressed approximately in the following formula: "If you want your son to take care of you in your old age and walk in straight paths, then admonish and discipline him in early childhood." At the same time, educators were warned not to "irritate children", not to cause them to freeze and hate, children should be sure that punishment, including corporal, is not directed against them as "persons", but against unseemly actions. Pedagogy is also a well-organized life in relationships. And experimenting with social life is an extremely serious matter and, as life itself has shown, not always within the power of entire nations and states.

A person - whether in the personality of a child, an adult, or as a representative of all humanity - was initially brought up in a rather rigid system of spiritual-practical and disciplinary-normative coordinates.

Most people, using the term "anxiety", do not even think about what it actually means. Many people, if asked to recall what exactly they felt in a state of anxiety, will say that they were tormented by bad feelings, experienced excitement, restlessness, and perhaps even trembled. The experience of anxiety entails a feeling of isolation and loneliness, some people include the emotion of sadness in the pattern of anxiety. It is important to remember that in a state of anxiety, we usually experience not one emotion, but a certain combination or pattern of different emotions, each of which affects our social relationships, thoughts and behavior. Many famous psychologists have studied anxiety. Such as Sigmund Freud, Karen Horney, Anna Freud, J. Taylor, A. Prikhozhan, Rollo May. It is anxiety, as many researchers and practical psychologists note, that underlies a number of psychological difficulties, including many developmental disorders that serve as a reason for seeking psychological services. The importance of anxiety correction and overcoming it is significant when preparing students for difficult situations (exams, competitions, etc.), when mastering a new activity. Anxiety is a relatively stable personality trait that characterizes the predisposition to perceive a fairly wide range of situations as threatening and to respond to them, as a rule, by developing a feeling of uneasiness, anxiety. Most often, the term "anxiety" is used to describe an unpleasant mental state in its coloring, which is characterized by

subjective feelings of tension, anxiety, gloomy forebodings, and from the physiological side is accompanied by the activation of the autonomic nervous system. Being a natural state, anxiety plays a positive role not only as an indicator of a disorder, but also as a mobilizer of mental reserves. To better distinguish between personal and situational anxiety, Spielberger designated the first as "T-property", and the second - as "T-state". Personal anxiety is a more permanent category and is determined by the type of higher nervous system, temperament, character, upbringing and acquired strategies for responding to external factors. Personal anxiety is inherent in an individual from birth, being one of the genetic personality traits. It can be considered as a personality trait manifested in a constant tendency to experience anxiety in a variety of life situations, including those that objectively do not dispose to it. The so-called situational anxiety develops throughout life as a reaction to the environment and events, i.e. generated by a specific situation that objectively causes anxiety. This condition can occur in any person on the eve of possible troubles and life complications. This condition is not only completely normal, but also plays a positive role. It acts as a kind of mobilizing mechanism that allows a person to seriously and responsibly approach solving emerging problems. Highly anxious students tend to perceive a threat to their self-esteem and life in a wide range of situations and react very tensely, with a pronounced state of anxiety. Anxiety largely determines the behavior of the student. There is a certain level of anxiety - a natural and obligatory feature of the active activity of the individual. The level of anxiety shows the student's internal attitude to a certain type of situation and gives indirect information about the nature of relationships with peers and adults. When this level exceeds the optimal, we can talk about the manifestation of increased anxiety. An increased level may indicate insufficient emotional adaptation to certain social situations. Students with this level of anxiety show an attitude towards themselves as weak, inept. Anxiety colors the attitude towards themselves, other people and reality in gloomy tones. Anxious students, as a rule, do not enjoy universal recognition in the group, but they do not find themselves in isolation, they are often among the least popular, as they are very often insecure, withdrawn, uncommunicative, or, on the contrary, over-communicative, annoying, or embittered. Another reason for their unpopularity is their lack of initiative due to their lack of self-confidence, therefore, these students cannot always be leaders in interpersonal relationships. The result of the lack of initiative of anxious students is that their peers develop a desire to dominate them, which leads to a decrease in the emotional background, a tendency to avoid communication, internal conflicts associated with the sphere of communication arise, and self-doubt increases. An insecure, anxious person is always suspicious, and suspiciousness gives rise to mistrust of others. He is afraid of others, expects an attack, ridicule, offense, which contributes to the formation of a psychological defense reaction in the form of aggression directed at others. This is expressed in the refusal to communicate and avoidance of persons who pose a "threat". Such students are usually lonely, withdrawn, and inactive. This affects the success of their studies and the establishment of contacts with the environment.

Anxious students are characterized by low self-esteem and self-respect, they do not believe in themselves and their strengths and feel lonely in this world, withdraw into themselves. And this contributes to the incomplete development of the student's personality and affects his status in the group. We conducted experimental work with college students studying in the first year. The total number of subjects is 92 people. According to the results of the study of the anxiety level of 1st year students using the technique "Situational and personal anxiety scale" it can be concluded that

47.8% of students have moderate situational anxiety, 28.3% - low, and 23.9% - high. We also found that 57.6% of students have moderate personal anxiety, 18.5 - low, and 23.9% - high. According to the result of the technique, it can be said that a quarter of first-year students are characterized by a high level of anxiety. Students with a high level of anxiety are distinguished by isolation and low sociability. As a rule, they are uninitiative, which is associated with the expectation of failure and low self-esteem. Conversely, students with a low level of anxiety are sociable and proactive, but they are characterized by weak emotional involvement in various life situations, restraint of feelings. The average level of anxiety indicates that these are more or less calm students, quite active and sociable, although there are cases when anxiety appears that is not justified by the current circumstances.

Recommendations for college teachers on optimizing the level of anxiety. In order to significantly reduce anxiety, it is necessary to ensure real success in any activity. Criticize less and encourage more, and do not compare with others, but only with yourself, evaluating the improvement of results. A gentle evaluation mode is necessary in the area in which the student's success is not great. Do not constantly focus on failures, but note the slightest success. Trusting contact and warm emotional relationships can also reduce general anxiety. It is necessary to study the system of personal relationships of a student in a group in order to purposefully form these relationships, to create a favorable emotional climate. Motivate such students to succeed, including them in social life.

REFERENCES

1. D. A. Karimova. Professional education of students. Pp. 100-101. Pedagogical science and its methodological problems in the context of modernity. (Collection of articles of the Republican scientific-theoretical conference. Navai-2012).
2. D. A. Karimova, O. M. Yariev Some ways to improve the effectiveness of the lesson. Pp. 92-94. Pedagogical science and its methodological problems in the context of modernity. (Collection of articles of the Republican scientific-theoretical conference. Navai-2012).